

Ransomware Attacks: Challenges and Defence

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Abstract—In line with the statistical reports examined, the damage caused by the total number of cyber-attack cases increasing every year around the world has reached incredible levels. The ransomware attack, which is one of these attacks, in this academic research; explaining its working principle and logic, damages and ways of protection were made, detailed information was given about the future of ransomware attacks, which is the main issue. Ransomware attacks will be able to be used as a threat to ransom demand of scams such as Deepfake Ransomware and Quantum cryptography which can have huge consequences, through developing technology and artificial intelligence soon. As a result, this research paper has been discussed to explain in detail what ransomware attacks will be now and in the near future, how to protect themselves from these attacks, and what needs to be done on an individual and company basis.

Keywords—ransomware, encryption, cyber-attacks, deepfake, quantum, protection, cryptography

I. INTRODUCTION

Cyber attacks lead to the emergence of new variations every year, due to the continuous development of hardware today and the use of devices to reach almost all masses. In this direction, there are various forms of cyber attacks for the purpose of attack. It can be said that factors such as ransom demand, protection methods and solution methods and methods vary according to the type of attack. In this world where all devices are connected via the Internet, the number of organized cybercriminal organizations that can reach victims is increasing day by day. According to IBM's report, the average cost of each data breach to companies or individuals is \$3.86 million [4]. According to another analysis report, Gartner, it is stated that the global information security market is estimated to reach \$170.4 billion in 2022 [3]. The statistical reports of these cyberattacks present us with a situation that cannot be taken lightly. It is possible for a company to lose all its reputation as a result of a cyber attack, and to collapse economically.

Ransomware attacks, one of the mentioned cyber attacks, emerged in 1989 with an attack under the name AIDS Info Disk Trojan, and many masses were infected with a floppy disk that was distributed only to 20,000 people at the WHO conference. There was an attack on victims' computers that demanded \$189 to be put in a mailbox with a warning [16]. This attack, which has a very old history, has reached very dangerous dimensions in today's world and continues to reach rapidly. As the types of spread to victims' devices and other details will be discussed later, it is necessary to look at another example. WannaCry, one of the biggest ransomware attacks ever, encrypts users' files with AES-128 cryptographic encryption method, as it can be seen in Figure [1], that it had a global impact and demanded an average of \$300-600 dollars in bitcoin, which was paid to the crypto account. This attack was carried out by targeting the vulnerability of ports 435 and

139 in the Server Message Block protocol in the Windows operating system. This attack, which created a crisis effect in various countries of the world, collapsed the British National Health System(NHS) and caused great damage to Spain's largest telecommunication company. However, it is stated in the reports that more than 40,000 organizations in China are affected by this situation [5]. The total loss to the victims of the WannaCry attack is thought to total \$4 billion so far [6].

This attack and similar ransomware attacks try not to leave their victims helpless by using the most advanced cryptography techniques. It can be said that even the most advanced devices of that year using Symmetric and Asymmetric encryption techniques required years of work to decrypt these passwords and ransomware [17,18]. Although the victims try to eliminate this cyber attack, the percentage of those who succeed is quite low. For example, 4 hours after the ransomware cyber attack took place, the victim is faced with the screen where the data is encrypted and requires a special password to be recovered, without realizing what is happening. If the necessary precautions have been taken, the data has been backed up and there are alternative ways to recover, there may be a chance to get rid of this situation without any problems. However, today, individual users and companies are constantly delaying or not doing these preparation stages "completely" [7].

The most important part of ransomware attacks is that quantum mechanics can be used in these attacks, as well as developing technology, hardware and advanced cryptographic algorithms. It's not hard to predict that ransomware will have huge ramifications in the future. The reason is Deepfake and Quantum issues. These two issues, which are considered quite new, are seen among the biggest threats of the future.

A. Deepfake Ransomware :

Deepfake method, which is the negative case brought to our lives by deep learning today, can produce unique content by using any user's image, audio or video through deep neural networks on computers with powerful graphics processing units. While this may sound very interesting at first glance, the Deepfake ransomware method creates a huge opportunity for attackers. In the future, this method will make it possible for political leaders, popular people or even the richest personalities and companies to lose their reputation. Attackers can pretend to do things that victims have never done (such as pornographic content, offensive acts, sound recordings that damage reputation, illegal videos) and threaten to publish these images and content [9]. This is a very difficult situation because the way you can defend against it is very limited.

Ransomware attacks, which received \$1 billion in ransom in 2016 [10], will now have the potential to generate billions of dollars with a single attack. This attack, which has the power to discredit a political leader and overthrow even governments, is in a very dangerous position [19-21]]. Today, while there is no clear solution method for distinguishing the

content created by the Deepfake method, it is predicted that it will be witnessed frequently by attackers threatening with ransomware attacks.

B. Quantum Cryptography

As it is known, quantum programming and quantum cryptographic encryption studies have become very popular in recent years. In the quantum world, it offers the possibility of doing some events that are considered impossible in the real world. To give a small example, it should be noted that the key pairs of 2048 bits, which are claimed to be unbreakable by today's computers, can currently decrypt even 4096-bit key-length encryptions of quantum computers using Shor's algorithm in a few hours. Quantum will shape the future and will sign many cases. If we foresee it, we can also guess that this area is very important in terms of encryption and security. The table below provides a table of comparisons and assumptions about time requires of crypto systems methods [8].

TABLE I.

LITERATURE-REPORTED ESTIMATES OF QUANTUM RESILIENCE FOR CURRENT CRYPTOSYSTEMS UNDER VARIOUS ASSUMPTIONS [11]

Crypto system	Category	Key Size	Quantum Algorithm	Time Required to Break
AES-GCM	Symmetric encryption	128 192 256	Grover's Algorithm	2.61×10^{12} yrs 1.97×10^{22} yrs 2.29×10^{32} yrs
RSA	Asymmetric encryption	1024 2048 4096	Shor's Algorithm	3.58 hours 28.63 hours 229 hours
ECC discrete-log	Assymmetric encryption	256 386 512	Shor's Algorithm	10.5 hours 37.67 hours 95 hours
SHA 256	Bitcoin mining	N/A	Grover's Algorithm	1.8×10^4 yrs
PBKDF2	Password hashing	N/A	Grover's Algorithm	2.3×10^7 yrs

Quantum encryption and decryption processes are among the first steps to be followed for attackers. The attackers, who use the methods and methods here for the security of their own attacks, want to leave their victims helpless in the face of near-impossible encryption. Apart from not only exploiting the attackers, many victims were also saved from the attack with quantum encryption [22-24]. Experts state that a mathematically possible encryption method or today's encryption methods based on mathematical principles can be cracked, and that they are not completely secure with developing systems and methods. It is foreseen that physics-based encryption methods will replace mathematics-based encryption methods. In this sense, it is claimed that 100% security will be provided [2].

In the next 10 years, it can be said that many things will change for this research paper, as the processing power of quantum computers in the coming years will be 100,000 times higher than that of today's quantum computers and the error rate will be 100 times less. For both victims and attackers. However, as it was stated years ago that this will happen, it would be very good for the whole world to prevent the work to be done in this field from being in favour of the aggressors [11].

II. WORKING PRINCIPLE OF RANSOMWARE ATTACK

There are many types of ransomware attacks that are independent of each other. Attackers sometimes make these attacks by tailoring them to specific people, and sometimes they produce automatic spyware that appeals to the general public and wait for their victims to fall into their trap. As a way of working; It is based on demanding ransom by obtaining and using important data as a result of attacks developed against popular companies, health institutions and mobile devices that they have chosen as their favourites. Attackers, who usually demand the ransom via Bitcoin, are avoiding all kinds of factors that may put them at risk. The best summarized version of this article can be seen in Figure 2. In the following, the categorized operating principle titles are explained.

Figure 1: Anatomy of a ransomware attack [1]

A. Spam Email Messages

This method is among the most used ways that allow ransomware attack to occur. There are the most well-known .doc, PDF, ZIP files or malicious software that redirects the web page, including the attackers who reach a very large audience via e-mail. When the malicious files in the attachments section are downloaded by the victim or the link is clicked, the malware infiltrates the victim's device, embeds itself in that device and begins to capture the attacker's important information on the device. [14]

B. Bootnets and Download Malicious Files

As users, we can assume that we have seen many advertisements such as "update", "your computer is not safe", "speed up your computer" that constantly appear on our computer or web pages after a file or program is downloaded and installed by a third party installer or server. These potentially ubiquitous malware installers aim to trick users into infiltrating the victim's device during the download and installation of programs. This attack hides and protects itself for a certain period of time after the installation is complete. It waits until it encrypts your important information and your computer and threatens you, and finally demands a ransom from the victim [13].

C. Operating System and Software Exploits

This method is more difficult and complex to defend than the previous two methods. Attackers infiltrate by exploiting the vulnerability of the operating system or any software on the device. Here, the device can be infiltrated without the

victim's knowledge, and the files can be locked by the attackers, and a ransom can be demanded [13]. The fact that security vulnerabilities have not been detected by the software manufacturer or that the victim has not made the latest software updates causes this working method to be easily used by attackers.

D. Executable Files

Although this infiltration method may seem like a file transfer via email, it was created specifically for .exe files to be modified by attackers for an infiltration attempt and to find victims online. Most of the time, when victims download third-party files online or try to download fake content, the names of these files are automatically changed to the file that the victim wants to download. When the victim tries to run and install the file without realizing that it is a .exe file, it can be said that the ransomware attack is integrated into the device.

III. RANSOMWARE ATTACK TYPES

There are different types of ransomware designed to meet the attacker's multiple purposes. These types are built on a certain architecture, aiming to create a structure that can demand ransom from the victim.

A. File Encrypting Ransomware

File encrypting ransomware are programs that leak a payload/file into your system and encrypt your files using techniques such as cryptoviral extortion, among others. These software take and encrypt your files and demand payment to decrypt and re-deliver them. The reason why this type of ransomware is so dangerous is that no security software or system restore can bring it back to you once cybercriminals have taken over your files. If you do not pay the ransom, you will lose this data. Even if you pay, there is no guarantee.

B. Non-Encrypting Ransomware

Ransomware programs that do not encrypt data focus on access. They work by restricting the organization's access to stolen data and information. It is also known that these software are supported by psychological factors, in some cases keeping users locked in their systems and exposing them to pornographic images.

C. Leakware

Malicious ransomware called Leakware does not encrypt data on the system. It provides unauthorized access to data, is used to demand ransom from the victim in exchange for not spreading or selling the data copied from the system. Despite not encrypting data, these attacks are highly dangerous, as they expose organizations to threats of reputational damage, disclosure of confidential information, large data breach penalties, and more. Leakware malware primarily targets institutions that have third-party information on the system that they are responsible for protecting. These include customer information, financial data, and more [12].

D. Mobile Ransomware

Given the popularity of ransomware on computer systems, it was only a matter of time before they were adapted to mobile devices, and it did. With these software, attackers specifically target Android devices that have the ability to download and install apps from unofficial third-party sources

[12]. In attacks where mobile ransomware is used, a person downloads the ransomware, which appears as an APK file of the application that they do not want to pay for, onto their device. The software runs a function that blocks other apps on mobile devices and displays a ransom message. Ransomware can also infect digital cameras by exploiting vulnerabilities in the picture transfer protocol (PTP).

IV. DEFENDING WAYS FROM RANSOMWARE ATTACKS

It is important to combine many factors in order to be protected from ransomware attacks, which attack in a variety of ways. Our system, which we consider to be "safe" at some points, can be subject to a security breach due to only a 1-byte missing. In order to prevent this, it is necessary to establish a self-updating system infrastructure that is always ready for new attacks, as it is said in the examples of Deepfake Ransomware and Quantum Cryptography. To explain the most important protection methods that can be counted in items;

A. Protection For Potential New Attacks In The Future

For Quantum and Deepfake methods, which will be popular in the coming years, it may be preferable to purchase antivirus or protection packages that do the most up-to-date research and provide sustainable protection [25-27]. They should be aware of these attacks and be followed up to date. In particular, it should be ensured that personal data (images and media) is stored in reliable cloud storage services. Make sure that the microphone and camera on the computers are turned off when not in use.

B. Mobile Device Security

The security of mobile devices is perhaps even more important than our personal computer in some cases. Now, bank, business, fund management, personal information (passport, identity info) card information, etc. samples can fall into the hands of the attacker when our phone is hacked.

To avoid this;

- The operating system should be constantly updated, and the latest security patches should be installed.
- Installing 3rd party applications carries great risk. These should be avoided
- Each application's own update should be updated from official links.
- Attention should be paid to the permissions that will be granted when a new application is installed, no permissions should be given to an unknown application [13].
- The device should be backed up at regular intervals.
- Mobile security apps must be installed.

C. General Protection For Business & Individual

As mentioned, there are many ways and types of ransomware attacks. As the most dangerous situation for the future, users may be threatened and ransom demanded with the Deepfake method, which is created with quantum encryption techniques. In order to get rid of this and similar techniques;

- Incorporating personnel who have worked in the field of quantum or newest security techniques.
- Regular security updates in this area
- Using the latest encryption and security methods
- Performing the backup operation
- Education and inform is one of the most important protection ways in the business security team.

People with personal computers;

- Using an antivirus program
- Don't prefer to installing 3rd party apps
- Taking regular backups.
- Making the latest security and operating system updates
- Avoid suspicious emails and attachments, use email protection applications and be aware the attacking method [15].

V. CONCLUSION

Contrary to today's attacks, this research paper focused on the most probable future attacks and a detailed study was carried out on this issue. In addition to explaining the ransomware attack types and methodology, it was emphasized that ransomware attacks are at a very dangerous level through statistical information, and it has been explained that the attackers are not far from the potential to earn billions of dollars in a few months in the near future. Developing technology and new generation encryption techniques allow ransomware attacks to be of different sizes. The most important work to be done in this area is to consider the aforementioned warnings and to carry out the most innovative protection in this area (Deepfake and Quantum Encryption). However, individual users should be warned and informed more about attacks in this area by application developers and websites. People should be aware of these when using applications and should not fall into the trap. Affordable solutions should be offered to attackers who especially evaluate the security vulnerabilities of small-medium enterprises, and the security of the company in every field should be dynamically ensured.

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